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WORK FOR FOREIGN STUDENTS IN UKRAINE

One of the most important issues that must be noted before making any decision and any step regarding work in Ukraine by applicants is knowing the unemployment rate in Ukraine. According to the information available from 1999 to 2018, the average unemployment rate in Ukraine was about 8.7 %. According to the latest statistics, the unemployment rate in Ukraine was about 9.92% which was announced in 2021[1].

The following occupations and jobs can increase your chance of getting a job in Ukraine:

-translator: people who can speak two or more languages can easily enter the Ukrainian job market;

-foreign language teacher: many Ukrainians want to have a command of a foreign language. For this reason, people who are professionals in this field can teach in institutes of this country;

- IT: it is a very successful field in the Ukrainian labor market.

Work in Ukraine for students

Work while studying is always one of the topics that international students can look at. Ukraine, like other European countries, allows students to work while studying, but this depends on certain conditions which we will discuss below. Students must obtain approval from the university and institution at which they study. The validity of a student's work in Ukraine depends on the student's residence permit. Students at the bachelor's and master's levels can obtain a work permit for a period of 20 hours per week, and doctoral students are also allowed to work 30 hours per week while studying in Ukraine.

One of the important factors that must be paid attention to before applying for a job in Ukraine is the monthly salaries of foreigners in Ukraine. The amount of monthly salaries of workers in Ukraine has decreased in recent years due to the political situation and the instability of the economy in Ukraine. This political and economic crisis started in 2013, which led to the closure of most companies in Ukraine [2].

There are many job opportunities in Ukraine in various fields. It is worth noting that Ukraine has a high educational level as well as the presence of many distinguished Arab cadres with high competencies in many institutions inside the country, therefore, working with them is considered one of the best options for obtaining permanent residence in the state, as well as for the reunification of all family members in addition to being able to apply for Ukrainian citizenship, but after at least five years of work and residence in the state have passed.

References:

1. <https://index.minfin.com.ua/labour/unemploy/>
2. <https://www.epravda.com.ua/rus/news/2020/09/25/665522/>

РОБОТА ДЛЯ ІНОЗЕМНИХ СТУДЕНТІВ В УКРАЇНІ

Одне з найважливіших питань, на яке слід звернути увагу перед прийняттям будь-якого рішення щодо роботи в Україні - це знання рівня безробіття в Україні. Але деякі професії можуть збільшити ваш успіх. Робота під час навчання - це завжди одна з тем, на яку можуть поглянути іноземні студенти. Одним із важливих факторів, на який слід звернути увагу перед тим, як подати заявку на вступ до України, є щомісячна заробітна плата іноземців в Україні. Розмір щомісячної заробітної плати робітників в Україні за останні роки зменшився через політичну ситуацію та нестабільність економіки в Україні.

Ключові слова: безробіття, професії, заробітна плата.

WORK FOR FOREIGN STUDENTS IN UKRAINE

One of the most important issues to consider before making any decision towards working in Ukraine is the level of unemployment in Ukraine. But some professions can increase your success. Work while studying is always one of the topics that foreign students can look at. One of the important factors to pay attention to before applying for Ukraine is the monthly salary of foreigners in Ukraine. The monthly wages of workers in Ukraine have declined in recent years due to the political situation and economic instability in Ukraine.

Key words: unemployment, professions, wages.